

THE IMPACT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE ON KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT VIA MANAGERIAL ACCOUNTING

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ABSTRACT

The current research work seeks to discover the influence of corporate governance on the management of knowledge and managerial accounting. It tries to scrutinize the transmitting role of managerial accounting in conveying the influence of corporate governance on the management of knowledge. The current study employed regression analyses and mediating procedures to analyze the relationships in the research model. The empirical findings reveal that, corporate governance structure imposes a statistical influence on the adoption of managerial accounting, which is in turn an antecedent of knowledge management. The mediating role of managerial accounting in conveying the effect of corporate governance to knowledge management is also discovered in this research. The results recommend that business executives should decide on appropriate practices of managerial accounting and the suitable acceptance of knowledge management in accordance with the current corporate governance structure, which can lead to competitive advantages for business.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Knowledge management, Managerial accounting

1. INTRODUCTION

Accounting is an important part of the economic and financial management system; therefore, in order for accounting to fully promote their functions of informing and inspecting to serve managers, each firm need to build a complete accounting system for itself, including financial accounting and managerial accounting (Chenhall & Langfield-Smith, 1998). In which, managerial accounting specializes in processing and providing accounting information to serve the performance of managers' functions such as planning, organization, checking and decision making. This contributes to overcoming shortcomings, backlogs, and implementing innovations in production and business in order to control the market, which ultimately improves the efficiency of production and business activities.

With the important role and function of managerial accounting as mentioned above, it is necessary for the firms to have a full awareness of managerial accounting and have a plan to apply this tool in business management (Phung Le Thuy, 2013). The application of managerial accounting in enterprises, however, depends on business conditions of enterprises; of which, the corporate governance structure is a very important factor affecting the level of managerial accounting application in enterprises (Wang & Huynh, 2014). According to Nham Phong Tuan and Nguyen Anh Tuan (2013), corporate governance is becoming a hot topic in discussions among government agencies and departments, especially when the Government is committed to promoting the equitisation process. An important factor to enhance the competitiveness of enterprises is financial transparency and the accountability of effective management principles. Moreover, corporate governance is also considered as a long-term catalyst to change the

business mindset of Vietnamese people, thereby better meeting the requirements of foreign investors and the global economy. In addition, a study by Huynh (2015) suggested and proved that, there is a very complex interrelationship between corporate governance and managerial accounting, in which corporate governance is the first factor determining the level of application of managerial accounting in enterprises. Furthermore, Sori (2009) analyzed the acceptance of managerial accounting practices and their contribution to knowledge management. The research result indicated the acceptance of managerial accounting practices could improve the functions of accounting in business that so augment information value. This will make significant usage of tacit and explicit knowledge to allow firms to make operative business decisions. Overall, managerial accounting works as an intermediate factor in transmitting the effect of corporate governance on knowledge management via itself.

In Vietnam, managerial accounting is still quite new, specifically managerial accounting has just appeared in Vietnam, starting when the Law on Accounting introduced the concept of managerial accounting, although it has appeared long ago in developed countries (Doan et al. 2011). Through the actual research and survey of a number of enterprises in Vietnam today, managerial accounting has initially received the attention of business leaders, however, it can be seen that there are still specific shortcomings that hinder the firm and application of managerial accounting in business (Phung Le Thuy, 2013). On the other hand, Sulaiman et al. (2004) emphasized that, there is still a lack of empirical research on managerial accounting practices in developing economies of Southeast Asia, including Vietnam, and that there is necessary to have more studies on the implementation of the above mentioned managerial accounting practices in business. Besides, Doan et al. (2011) said that the number of studies on managerial accounting practices in Vietnam is very modest, and suggested that scholars should conduct more research on managerial accounting practices in this country, especially studies on the relationship between corporate governance, managerial accounting and the management of knowledge. In Vietnam so far, however, there seems to be no research on the role of corporate governance in the level of managerial accounting application and the management of knowledge in business. More importantly, no research on the role of managerial accounting in the research model has been undertaken. Therefore, studying the effects of corporate governance on the usage of managerial accounting tools and the management of knowledge in business is very meaningful for enterprises in Vietnam.

2. CORPORATE GOVERNANCE ON KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT VIA MANAGERIAL ACCOUNTING

Mayer (1997) referred to corporate governance as methods of taking the benefits of stakeholders and executives into line as well as confirming, corporations are operated for the interests of shareholders. Corporate governance is regularly focused on the configuration and purpose of administrative boards. According to Cadbury (1992), corporate governance is viewed as an observing instrument to diminish the agency costs as a result of the difference in ownership with management, and thus increase corporate effectiveness. Cassell (2012) assessed the corporate governance structure on the composition of administrative boards, and on the role of the chairperson of administrative boards.

Salvato and Melin (2008) confirmed decentralization of administration to independent executives who had excellent professional qualifications and good work experience will increase the level of formality of documents used in the enterprise. Independent directors are often required to report periodically and extraordinarily to the Board of Directors and major Shareholders. Therefore, they must apply standard management tools to effectively control business activities of enterprises (Cromie et al. 1995). On the other hand, Christine et al. (2011) conducted a research on corporate governance and managerial accounting and suggested that it is necessary to set up a single division to be responsible for managerial accounting in enterprises in which formal managerial accounting methods are applied. Their research results also showed that the professional level of independent directors has a relation with the level of application of complex managerial accounting tools. In addition, Agrawal and Chadha (2005) found evidence of the ability to edit financial accounting statements in enterprises where the members of the board of directors and the supervisory board as the majority of independent experts was lower than that of other enterprises. This evidence is consistent with the argument that independent directors tend to use formal managerial accounting tools which produce more truthful financial statements. Moreover, the fact that the chairperson of the managerial board concurrently holds the position of the general director has an important role in influencing the acceptance of managerial accounting tools. The abovementioned arguments lead to the proposition that corporate governance likely determines the adoption of managerial accounting. Moreover, Sam et al. (2012) elicited the separation of chairmen plays a vital role in making business decisions on the acceptance of managerial accounting systems and recommended a tie between the implementation of managerial accounting systems and the role of chairmen.

Managerial accounting is an instrument designed to deliver both financial and non-financial information to enterprises (Ajibolade et al. 2010). This information will help managers make more accurate business decisions. According to Kaplan (1983), managerial accounting tools are considered as part of the corporate management system. Their role is to provide suitable information for managerial planning and control to augment organizational performance. A study by Lucas (1997) suggested that managerial accounting is a very useful tool to provide accurate and complete information for business planning and management in the highly dynamic environment today. Based on the above authors' point of view, this research determines the level of application of managerial accounting tools in enterprises, the extent to which enterprises choose and implement managerial accounting tools in their businesses. On the other hand, Mayer (1997) defined corporate governance as the mechanisms and regulations through which enterprises are operated and controlled. According to Cadbury (1992), the corporate governance structure indicates the rights and responsibilities among different members of the enterprise, including shareholders, boards of directors and other stakeholders.

Klein and Prusak (1994) referred to the intellectual capital as valuable knowledge; while other scholars (Sullivan, 2000; Kok, 2007) indicated intellectual capital creates knowledge. Hereafter, the bond between managerial accounting and the management of knowledge may be considered correspondingly to the tie between managerial accounting and the intellectual capital. Likewise, Tayles et al. (2002) examined the bond between the management of

intellectual capital and the adoption of managerial accounting in business, suggested the acceptance of managerial accounting will support management of intellectual capital. Regarding the bond between accounting information methods and management of knowledge, Sori (2009) tried to scrutinize the usage of accounting information practices and their contribution to knowledge management, and revealed that the usage of managerial accounting systems would improve the functions of accounting in business and enhance information value. Automated accounting information practices can boost the process of producing financial reports and deal with human weaknesses in data processing. Accounting information practices make considerable use of tacit and explicit knowledge to enable firms to make effective business decisions. Novas et al. (2012) investigated the impact of management accounting on the implementation of intellectual capital, focusing on the critical function of managerial accounting in the development of intellectual capital. The empirical findings exposed a statistically positive influence of managerial accounting on applying intellectual capital or management of knowledge.

Birkett (1995) emphasized the change in managerial accounting over the last few years. Traditionally, the emphasis of managerial accounting has been on accounting information. Accounting data was used by managerial accountants to assist in planning and management. Traditional managerial accounting procedures have been called into question. Corporations have begun to integrate suppliers as well customers into the firm's business decisions. Therefore, the tie of managerial accounting to knowledge management should be established. It can then recommend that the acceptance of managerial accounting could affect the implementation of knowledge management. Overall, the acceptance of managerial accounting in business is an antecedent of adopting knowledge management, but it is a consequence of corporate governance. Therefore it can suggest corporate governance can affect the implementation of knowledge management via the acceptance of managerial accounting.

3. DATA COLLECTION

The data used in the current research were primary data collected from a questionnaire survey. According to Hoang Trong and Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2008), with a reliability of 95% and a statistical error of 5%, the sample size is supposed to be 385. From the above results, the sample size was 385 observations. In order to ensure that the number of survey sheets collected is fully met with the necessary information for the research and has a sufficient sample size, however, this research conducted a survey of 500 enterprises. Enterprises were selected by random sampling method among companies listed on 3 major stock exchanges of Vietnam. Finally, only 423 collected survey sheets met the information requirements for analyses in this research.

4. MEASUREMENTS

Corporate Governance (CGO) is computed on the proportion of independent directors (CGO1) and the separation of chairman positions (CGO2). That are adapted from (Cassell 2012). The majority of independent directors takes 1 if the percentage of independent executives is more than 50%, otherwise as 0. The separation of chairman positions takes 1 if the positions of

chairman and chief executive officer are separate, otherwise as 0. Managerial accounting (MAA) is estimated with a five-point scale. This is modified from Cinquini et al. (2008). MAA is composed of six items. MAA1 is traditional budgeting, MAA2 is cost volume profit analysis, MAA3 is activity based costing, MAA4 is total quality management, MAA5 is variance analysis, and MAA6 is balanced scorecard. That is adapted from the prior research (Lucas 1997; Al-Omiri & Drury 2007). Knowledge management (KNM) is calculated with a five-point scale on five items, which is adapted from Lin and Lee (2005). KNM1 is the distribution of knowledge among managers and juniors. KNM2 is the distribution of knowledge among coworkers. KNM3 is the distribution of knowledge across the divisions. KNM4 is the efficacious monitoring of diverse sources and forms of knowledge. KNM5 is employing knowledge in everyday usage.

5. ANALYTIC TECHNIQUES

The research model analyzed the associations among corporate governance, management accounting, and management of knowledge. In which, the factor of corporate governance structure includes two observed items, the factor of managerial accounting application is composed of six observed items, and the factor of knowledge management consists of five observed items. The information for these observed items was collected from enterprises selected on three major stock exchanges of Vietnam. After that, the collected data was analyzed using SPSS 18 software. First, the data was checked for reliability with the techniques of reliability analysis and exploratory factor analysis. Reliability analysis is a statistical technique used to statistically analyze the appropriateness of observed items representing the key variables they constitute. Meanwhile, exploratory factor analysis is performed to check the suitability between the key factors/variables. Then, the hypotheses in the research model were tested by linear regression analysis techniques. These analyses are used to check the suitability of regression model and statistical hypotheses that are supported or rejected by the collected data set. Finally, mediating analyses were applied to scrutinize the transmitting role of managerial accounting in the effect of corporate governance on knowledge management.

6. RESEARCH RESULTS

Table 1: Reliability analysis

Factor	Observed item	Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
MAA	MAA1	.754	.861
	MAA2	.652	
	MAA3	.637	
	MAA4	.628	
	MAA5	.627	
	MAA6	.645	
KNM	KNM1	.728	.886
	KNM2	.738	
	KNM3	.707	
	KNM4	.722	
	KNM5	.736	

Reliability analysis technique is used to statistically analyze the suitability of observed items that represent the main variable they constitute. The outcomes of the reliability analysis are exhibited in Table 1. The figures from Table 1 show that the correlation coefficients of the observed items in the scale are all greater than the 0.5 value. This proves that observed items of a scale are similar (Hair, 2011). In addition, the Cronbach's alpha results show that the components of the scale have high and good reliability coefficient which is greater than 0.7 (Hair, 2011). All 9 observed items meet the reliability requirements, so all of them are included in exploratory factor analysis to check the suitability among the main factors/variables. The results of the exploratory factor analysis technique are revealed in Table 2, with factor coefficients less than 0.3 that are not shown.

The results from Table 2 show that the exploratory factor analyses have grouped the observed items into two main factors, consistent with the original theoretical framework. Specifically, the managerial accounting factor is formed from six eleven observed items have factor coefficients greater than 0.5, which satisfies the convergence of each factor (Hair, 2011). Besides, the difference between the factor coefficient of an observed item with the main factor and the remaining factors is greater than 0.3, which satisfies the divergence among factors (Hair, 2011). The common coefficients of all observed items are all greater than 0.5; so, they all satisfy the conditions of exploratory factor analysis (Hair, 2011). The P_{value} is 0.000, less than 1% and the KMO coefficient is 0.829, greater than 0.7, proving that the exploratory factor analysis for the research data set is suitable and reaches the statistically significant level of 1%. All of the abovementioned criteria show that the data set used for this research satisfies the required level of reliability. After the data set used for this research satisfied the level of reliability according to statistical requirements, they continued to be analyzed by linear regression analyses to test the hypotheses in the research model. The linear regression analyses produced the results as described in Tables 3 & 4.

Table 2: Exploratory factor analysis

Factor	Observed item	Factor coefficient		Common coefficient
MAA	MAA1	.828		.708
	MAA2	.750		.592
	MAA3	.761		.582
	MAA4	.762		.581
	MAA5	.746		.565
	MAA6	.726		.588
KNM	KNM1		.820	.686
	KNM2		.826	.704
	KNM3		.812	.667
	KNM4		.826	.690
	KNM5		.822	.695
KMO	.868			
P _{value}	.000			

The linear regression results presented in Tables 3 & 4 showed that the determination coefficients of R^2 are equal to 0.174 and 0.081, which means that the corporate governance elements of CGO1 and CGO2 explain 17.4% of the variation in managerial accounting variable that in turn explain 8.1% of the variation in the knowledge management variable.

Table 3: Regression analysis

	β	S.E.	t	P _t	VIF
Constant	2.842	.059	47.970	.000	
GCO1	.473	.087	5.459	.000	1.480
GCO2	.179	.087	2.047	.041	1.480
Durbin-Watson	1.888				
$\chi^2/P\chi^2$.631/.374				
R^2	.174				
F/P _F	34.561/.000				

* Dependent Variable: MAA

The Fisher coefficients are 34.561 and 28.734 at the 1% significance level, implying that the research models are suitable at the 1% significant level. Moreover, the Durbin-Watson coefficients attain the values of 1.888 and 1.891 falling in the interval from d_u to $(4 - d_u)$; indicating no autocorrelation. The coefficients of χ^2 from the Breusch–Pagan test attain the values of 0.631 and 0.422 at the 0.374 and 0.547 significance levels that surpass the 10% level, demonstrating no heteroskedasticity. In addition, the values of VIF are all less than 2, showing no multicollinearity.

Table 4: Regression analysis

	β	S.E.	t	P _t	VIF
Constant	3.493	.173	20.162	.000	
MAA	.281	.052	5.360	.000	1.000
Durbin-Watson	1.891				
$\chi^2/ P\chi^2$.422/.547				
R ²	.081				
F/P _F	28.734/.000				

* Dependent Variable: KNM

Table 3 also proves that the influences of the corporate governance variables of CGO1 and CGO2 on the managerial accounting variable are at the statistically significant levels of 1% and 5%, with influential coefficients of 0.473 and 0.179 respectively. Table 4 indicates that the impact of the managerial accounting variable on the management of knowledge is at the statistically significant level of 1%, with an influential coefficient of 0.281. Thus, the linear regression analyses offer statistical supports for the hypotheses. The adoption of managerial accounting in enterprises is partly determined by the corporate governance structure; but it is an antecedent of knowledge management. To analyze the mediating role of managerial accounting on the linkage between corporate governance and knowledge management, first regression analyses were employed. The results are shown in Tables 5 & 6. Based on the determination coefficients of R², the Fisher coefficients, the Durbin-Watson coefficients, the coefficients of χ^2 , the values of VIF, and P values, it can suggest the research models in Tables 5 & 6 gain goodness of fit to the data. It can be seen when included into the research model in Table 6, MAA decreases the influences of the corporate governance variables of CGO1 and CGO2 on the managerial accounting variable from 0.392 and 0.349 down to 0.338 and 0.329 respectively.

Table 5: Regression analysis

	β	S.E.	t	P _t	VIF
Constant	3.963	.057	69.123	.000	
CGO1	.392	.084	4.666	.000	1.480
CGO2	.349	.084	4.136	.000	1.480
Durbin-Watson	1.901				
$\chi^2/ P\chi^2$.745/.291				
R ²	.215				
F/P _F	45.009/.000				

* Dependent Variable: KNM

In concurrence with Baron and Kenny (1986), it could suggest the acceptance of managerial accounting likely mediates the linkage between corporate governance and the management of knowledge. The mediating procedures stipulated by Goodman (1960) were applied to examine the statistical significance for the interceding impacts. The outcomes are displayed in Table 7.

Table 6: Regression analysis

	β	S.E.	t	P_t	VIF
Constant	3.643	.161	22.561	.000	
CGO1	.338	.087	3.879	.000	1.614
CGO2	.329	.084	3.893	.000	1.498
MAA	.113	.053	2.120	.035	1.211
Durbin-Watson	1.900				
$\chi^2/ P\chi^2$.801/.254				
R ²	.226				
F/P _F	31.825/.000				

* Dependent Variable: KNM

The empirical figures point out, the implementation of managerial accounting statistically mediates the effects of the corporate governance items of CGO1 and CGO2 on the management of knowledge at the 1% & 10% levels with the coefficients of 0.160 and 0.058 respectively. It can then suggest that, managerial accounting transmits a partial influence of corporate governance on knowledge management via itself.

Table 7: Mediating analyses

Mediating variable	Linkage	Coefficient	S.E.	t	P
MAA	CGO1 → KNM	.160	.050	3.197	.0014
MAA	CGO2 → KNM	.058	.031	1.869	.0615

7. CONCLUSION

Corporate governance is a vital factor in the acceptance of managerial accounting and the management of knowledge. In Vietnam, however, there are almost no studies analyzing the relationship between corporate governance structure, the approval of managerial accounting and the management of knowledge. Consequently, the current research focuses on studying the causal relationship among corporate governance structure, the application of managerial accounting and the management of knowledge in business; in which the corporate governance structure is the factor that affects the acceptance of managerial accounting, which in turn stimulates the acceptance of knowledge management. The current project applied statistical techniques such as reliability, exploratory factor, linear regression and mediating analyses to analyze and evaluate the influence of the corporate governance structure on the acceptance of managerial accounting and management of knowledge in business. The empirical results of this research are consistent with the results of previous studies on the causal relationship among the corporate governance and the application of managerial accounting and knowledge management. The research results of this work will help scholars study management and accounting as well as help leaders of Vietnamese enterprises have a deeper and more general understanding of the relationship among the corporate governance, the application of managerial accounting and management of knowledge in business. It will help to give some useful management implications for business managers in applying managerial accounting and

knowledge management in business. This research also implies that business managers should choose suitable managerial accounting systems and the appropriate acceptance of knowledge management in business in accordance with the current corporate governance structure of their enterprises. This can help enterprises gain reasonable advantages over their competitors. As a result, enterprises will increasingly improve their organizational efficiency.

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